

Heat Exchanger and Nanofluids: Last Ten Years Journey and Bibliometrics Analysis

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Abstract

The present research work is devoted to bibliometric analysis for the keyword heat exchanger and nanofluids for last ten years research work obtained from dimensions ai data base, with the help of VOSviewer software. For this purpose, after data extraction from the database, country wise publication and citation analysis, organization wise publication and citation analysis, and journal wise publication and citation analysis was conducted, and top 20 results were analyzed in details. The results of the research work showed the increasing trends in research activities in the proposed field, as well as greater involvement of gulf countries as well as India in the field, during last five years.

Keywords: Heat exchanger, Nanofluids, Bibliometrics, VOS viewer, database, dimensions.ai.

1. Introduction

According to Nivedini et al. (2020), the industrial sector mainly functions on the usage of thermal energy for their heating and cooling systems. Heat transfer magnification is demanded in many industrial applications (Karuppasamy et al., 2019). According to Venkatraman et al. (2021), nowadays ensure the performance of heat exchanger is one of the toughest roles in industries, for which a lot of research activities are going all over the world. Here are some key needs and requirements for heat exchangers:

- a) **Temperature Control:** Heat exchangers are used to control temperatures in processes where precise temperature regulation is essential. They allow for the transfer of heat between fluids to achieve desired temperatures, whether it's heating or cooling;
- b) **Energy Efficiency:** Heat exchangers play a vital role in energy conservation by capturing and reusing heat that would otherwise be wasted. They help industries optimize energy usage and reduce operational costs;

- c) **Process Optimization:** In many industrial processes, maintaining specific temperatures is crucial for optimal performance and product quality. Heat exchangers facilitate this by efficiently transferring heat between different process streams;
- d) **Heat Recovery:** Heat exchangers are employed for heat recovery applications where waste heat from one process is utilized to preheat or heat another process stream. This improves overall energy efficiency and reduces environmental impact;
- e) **Space and Weight Considerations:** In applications where space and weight are limited, such as automotive and aerospace industries, compact and lightweight heat exchangers are essential. They allow for efficient heat transfer while minimizing size and weight;
- f) **Corrosion Resistance:** Heat exchangers must be designed to withstand corrosion, especially when handling corrosive fluids. Materials selection and proper coatings are crucial to ensure longevity and reliability;
- g) **Pressure Drop:** Depending on the application, heat exchangers should be designed to minimize pressure drop while maximizing heat transfer efficiency. This ensures smooth operation and optimal performance of the entire system;
- h) **Cleanability and Maintenance:** Heat exchangers should be designed for easy cleaning and maintenance to prevent fouling and ensure long-term performance. Removable components and access points are essential for periodic inspection and servicing;
- i) **Environmental Regulations:** Compliance with environmental regulations regarding emissions and energy efficiency often dictates the design and operation of heat exchangers. Meeting these standards is critical for regulatory compliance and sustainability; and
- j) **Cost-effectiveness:** Cost is always a significant factor in the selection of heat exchangers. The design, materials, and operational efficiency should be balanced to provide the most cost-effective solution for a given application.

There are several types of heat exchangers, each with its own design and operating principles. Here are some common types:

- a) **Shell and Tube Heat Exchangers:** This is one of the most common types of heat exchangers. It consists of a bundle of tubes enclosed in a shell. One fluid flows through the tubes, while the other flows around the outside of the tubes within the shell. Shell and tube

heat exchangers are versatile and widely used in various industries due to their efficiency and ease of maintenance;

- b) **Plate Heat Exchangers:** Plate heat exchangers consist of multiple thin plates with corrugated surfaces arranged in a frame. Fluids flow alternately between the plates, allowing for efficient heat transfer. Plate heat exchangers are compact, lightweight, and suitable for applications where space is limited;
- c) **Finned Tube Heat Exchangers:** Finned tube heat exchangers enhance heat transfer by adding fins to the outer surface of the tubes. The fins increase the surface area available for heat exchange, improving efficiency. Finned tube heat exchangers are commonly used in air-cooled applications, such as HVAC systems and refrigeration;
- d) **Double Pipe Heat Exchangers:** Double pipe heat exchangers consist of two concentric pipes with fluid flowing in opposite directions. They are simple in design and suitable for low to moderate-pressure applications. Double pipe heat exchangers are often used in small-scale and low-cost applications;
- e) **Air-cooled Heat Exchangers:** Air-cooled heat exchangers use ambient air as the cooling medium to remove heat from a process fluid. They consist of finned tubes exposed to the airflow. Air-cooled heat exchangers are commonly used in applications where water availability is limited or where environmental regulations restrict water usage;
- f) **Plate-Fin Heat Exchangers:** Plate-fin heat exchangers use stacked plates with fins to increase the surface area available for heat transfer. They are compact and lightweight, making them suitable for high-pressure and high-temperature applications in industries such as aerospace and oil refining;
- g) **Regenerative Heat Exchangers:** Regenerative heat exchangers are used for heat recovery applications where heat from one fluid stream is transferred to another fluid stream through a rotating matrix or bed of solid material. They are commonly used in processes where high-temperature exhaust gases can be used to preheat incoming air or other fluids; and
- h) **Spiral Heat Exchangers:** Spiral heat exchangers have a coiled design, allowing for a compact footprint and efficient heat transfer. They are suitable for high-viscosity fluids and can handle high fouling applications due to their self-cleaning design.

Each type of heat exchanger has its advantages and limitations, and the selection depends on factors such as the application requirements, operating conditions, space constraints, and budget considerations.

Enhancement of heat transfer with high rate and reduction of energy losses is most important for researchers to deal with the energy wastage problems. For that Extended surface technologies such as fins, micro channels with common automobiles, electronic machineries are reaching to their limits. The advanced techniques require special type of surface geometries or fluid additives to increase the heat transfer rate. Conventional coolants which are used in different type of heat exchanger such as water, engine oil, ethylene glycol etc. have poor or low heat transfer rate. Therefore, new technologies which have potential to improve the thermal properties of cooling fluids are of great interest to the researchers.

To overcome this drawback and to increase the rate of heat transfer there is a strong motivation to develop advanced heat transfer fluids with substantially higher conductivities to enhance thermal characteristics. Small particles (nano particles) of different material such as Al_2O_3 , CuO etc. stay suspended much longer than larger particles in base fluid. As such an innovative way in improving thermal conductivities of a fluid is to suspend metallic nano particles within it. The resulting mixture referred to as a nano fluid possesses a substantially larger thermal conductivity compared to that of traditional fluids (Babar et al., 2024).

According to Vallejo et al. (2022), the research on nano fluids has increased markedly in the last two decades. Initial attention has focused on conventional or mono nano fluids, dispersions of one type of solid nano-sized particles in a base fluid. Despite various challenges such as dispersion stability or increased pumping power, nano fluids have become improved working fluids for various energy applications. According to Porgar et al. (2023), use of nanofluids enhances fluid heat efficiency and also reduces energy consumption.

The present research work is devoted to the bibliometric analysis for heat exchangers and nanofluids, in order to investigate the scenario of research in the field. The research paper portrays the details of bibliometric analysis followed by discussion, and conclusion, limitations and future scope of the research.

2. Bibliometric Analysis

The present bibliometric analysis was conducted on the open source database www.dimensions.ai, which provides free and downloadable bibliometric resources for helping the researchers belonging to different streams. For this purpose, the search terms used was heat exchanger and nanofluids, as a result of which the results numbers of research papers published in last ten were obtained, presented as follows.

Figure 2.1: Numbers of Research Publications for Different Years

The results obtained also displayed numbers of journals belonging to different fields as well as research articles belonging to those journals. Figure 2.2 presents details of number of journals, their streams as well as number of publications, belonging to those journals.

Figure 2.2: Number of Research Publications from Different Streams and Number of Journals

The present bibliometric analysis was based on country wise publication and citation analysis, organization wise publication and citation analysis, and journal wise publication and citation analysis, the details of which are portrayed in upcoming sub-sections.

2.1 Country wise Publication and Citation Analysis

In the next stage, on analyzing the extracted dimensions.ai data in VOSviewer, number of publications as well as citations appeared in last ten years for different countries were obtained, the details of which are presented Table 2.1 for top twenty alternatives.

Table 2.1: Number of Publications and Citations for Different Countries in last ten years

S. No	Rank	Country	Number of Publications	Rank	Country	Number of Citations
1.	1	Saudi Arabia	468	1	China	14306

2.	2	China	463	2	United States	12770
3.	3	India	410	3	Iran	10902
4.	4	Pakistan	384	4	Saudi Arabia	9389
5.	5	Iran	339	5	India	8675
6.	6	United States	211	6	Pakistan	8507
7.	7	Egypt	205	7	South Korea	5260
8.	8	Malaysia	180	8	Malaysia	5139
9.	9	Turkey	119	9	United Kingdom	4838
10.	10	United Kingdom	112	10	Egypt	3881
11.	11	Iraq	100	11	Vietnam	3483
12.	12	Thailand	94	12	Thailand	3036
13.	13	Vietnam	93	13	Turkey	2343
14.	14	South Korea	86	14	Canada	2285
15.	15	United Arab Emirates	73	15	Australia	2052
16.	16	Australia	71	16	United Arab Emirates	2037
17.	17	Canada	65	17	Iraq	1542
18.	18	Romania	44	18	Romania	1322
19.	19	Portugal	33	19	Portugal	1020
20.	20	Kuwait	29	20	Kuwait	949

Figure 2.3 shows the details of results in graphical format.

(a) Number of Publications from Different Countries

(b) Number of Citations from Different Countries

Figure 2.3: Details of Publications and Citations for Different Countries

Moving one step further, on drawing network, overlay and density visualizations for above information, the following outputs were obtained.

(a) Network Visualization for Publications from Different Countries

(b) Overlay Visualizations for Publications from Different Countries

(c) Density Visualizations for Different Countries

Figure 2.4: Network, Overlay and Density Visualizations of Research Publications for Different Countries

2.2 Organization wise Publication and Citation Analysis

In the next stage, on analyzing the extracted dimensions.ai data in VOSviewer, number of publications as well as citations appeared in last ten years for different organizations were obtained, the details of which are presented Table 2.2 for top twenty alternatives.

Table 2.2: Number of Publications and Citations for Different Organizations in last ten years

S. No	Rank	Organization	Number of Publications	Rank	Organization	Number of Citations
1.	1	King Khalid University	115	1	Ton Duc Thang University	3039
2.	2	Prince Sattam Bin Abdulaziz University	100	2	Quaid – I-Azam University	2978

3.	3	King Abdulaziz University	93	3	King Abdulaziz University	2624
4.	4	Ton Duc Thang University	74	4	University of Malaya	2608
5.	5	Quaid – I-Azam University	64	5	King Mongkut's University of Technology	2592
6.	6	Anna University, Chennai	63	6	King Khalid University	2501
7.	7	King Mongkut's University of Technology	61	7	King Fahd University of Petroleum and	1567
8.	8	King Saud University	59	8	Islamic Azad University, Tehran	1505
9.	9	Future University in Egypt	58	9	Prince Sattam Bin Abdulaziz University	1401
10.	10	Umm al-qura University	57	10	Kermanshah University of Technology	1319
11.	11	University of Malaya	45	11	Anna University, Chennai	1154
12.	12	Majmaah University	41	12	Islamic Azad University of Khomeynish	1048
13.	13	Islamic Azad University, Tehran	37	13	City University of Science and Information Technology	907
14.	14	King Fahd University of Petroleum and Engineering	37	14	Indian Insittute of Technology, Varanasi	899

15.	15	Islamic Azad University of Khomeynish	28	15	Majmaah University	871
16.	16	City University of Science and Information Technology	27	16	Umm al-qura University	803
17.	17	Kermanshah University of Technology	26	17	GLA University	637
18.	18	Prince Mohammad Bin Fahd University	25	18	Future University in Egypt	632
19.	19	GLA University	19	19	Prince Mohammad Bin Fahd University	574
20.	20	Indian Insittute of Technology, Varanasi	18	20	King Saud University	545

Figure 2.5 shows the details of results in graphical format.

(a) Number of Publications from Different Organizations

(b) Number of Citations from Different Organizations

Figure 2.5: Details of Publications and Citations for Different Organizations

Moving one step further, on drawing network, overlay and density visualizations for above information, the following outputs were obtained.

(d) Network Visualization for Publications from Different Organizations

(e) Overlay Visualizations for Publications from Different Organizations

(f) Density Visualizations for Different Organizations

Figure 2.6: Network, Overlay and Density Visualizations of Research Publications for Different Organizations

2.3 Journals wise Publication and Citation Analysis

In the next stage, on analyzing the extracted dimensions.ai data in VOSviewer, number of publications as well as citations appeared in last ten years for different Journals were obtained, the details of which are presented Table 2.3 for top twenty alternatives.

Table 2.3: Number of Publications and Citations for Different Journals in last ten years

S. No	Rank	Journal	Number of Publications	Rank	Journal	Number of Citations
1.	1	Scientific reports	323	1	Scientific reports	5472
2.	2	Nanomaterials	194	2	Nanomaterials	3147
3.	3	Heliyon	152	3	Discover nano	3037
4.	4	Micromachiens	116	4	International	1914

				communications in heat transfer		
5.	5	Journal of thermal analysis and calorimetry	48	5	Heliyon	1589
6.	6	Discover nano	43	6	Renewable and sustainable energy reviews	1507
7.	7	International communications in heat transfer	28	7	Applied thermal engineering	1471
8.	8	Materials today proceedings	27	8	Experimental thermal and fluid science..	1422
9.	9	Applied thermal engineering	23	9	Micromachiens	1302
10.	10	Heat and mass transfer	22	10	Journal of thermal analysis and calorimetry	1277
11.	11	Heat transfer research	22	11	International journal of heat and mass transfer	1267
12.	12	International journal of heat and mass transfer	17	12	Energy conversion and management	969
13.	13	International journal of thermal sciences	15	13	Advanced powder technology	543
14.	14	Experimental thermal and fluid science..	14	14	Powder technology	461
15.	15	Case studies in thermal	13	15	International journal of thermal sciences	398

engineering						
16.	16	International journal of numerical methods	10	16	Case studies in thermal engineering	368
17.	17	Powder technology	10	17	Materials today proceedings	367
18.	18	Energy conversion and management	9	18	Heat and mass transfer	330
19.	19	Renewable and sustainable energy reviews	8	19	Heat transfer research	183
20.	20	Advanced powder technology	7	20	International journal of numerical methods	30

Figure 2.7 shows the details of results in graphical format.

(b) Number of Publications from Different Organizatins

(b) Number of Citations from Different Journals

Figure 2.7: Details of Publications and Citations for Different Journals

Moving one step further, on drawing network, overlay and density visualizations for above information, the following outputs were obtained.

(g) Network Visualization for Publications from Different Journals

(h) Overlay Visualizations for Publications from Different Journals

(i) Density Visualizations for Different Journals

Figure 2.8: Network, Overlay and Density Visualizations of Research Publications for Different Journals

3. Discussion

Country wise publication and citation analysis tells about the rankings of the countries for the number of research publications as well as citations. The analysis tells that, out of 20 countries, on the basis of number of publications, the country Saudi Arabia scores the maximum rank with the number of publications is equal to 468, while Kuwait scores the least rank with the number of publications is equal to 29. On the other hand, for the criteria, number of citations, China scores the first rank with 14306 citations, whereas Kuwait again gets the minimum rank with number of citations is equal to 949.

From network visualization diagram, one can easily investigate the citation relationships among different countries. After analyzing overlay visualizations for publications from different countries, one can find easily find that Saudi Arabia is a leading alternative for publishing the maximum number of research publications in recent years. In the similar manner, from density visualizations, one can easily investigate that Saudi Arabia, China, India, Iran and Pakistan are at leading positions in case of research publications.

As a result of organization based publication and citation analysis, one can easily find that King Khalid University shows the maximum number of publications (115), and scores rank 1st whereas Indian Institute of Technology, Varanasi offers minimum number of publications (18), and scores the rank 20. Proceeding in the similar manner, it can also be found that in case of number of citations, Ton Duc Thang University scores the rank 1st rank with 3039 citations, whereas King Saud University scores the rank 20 with the minimum number of citations (545). After analyzing overlay visualizations for different organizations, one can easily find that King Khalid University, Prince Sattam Bin Abdulaziz University, Future Univeristy, King Saudi Univeristy, and Ummm Al-qura Univeristy, are more actively involved in research activitie. After analyzing, the density visualizations, one can easily investigate that Kind Khalid University, Prince Sattam Bin Abdulaziz University, King Abdulaziz Univerisy and Ton Duc Thang Univeristy, are under leading positions in case of research publications. In the list of rankings, three Indian organizations, namely Anna University, GLA University and Indian Institute of Technology, Varanasi were also appeared, which shows the active contributions of Indian researchers in the field of heat exchangers and nanofluids.

After analyzing the details of publications and citations from different journals in last ten years, one can investigate that the journal Scientific Reports scores the first rank with the maximum number of research publications (323), whereas the journal Advanced Powder Technology shows the minimum rank with 7 research publications. Proceeding in the similar manner, one can easily find that the journal Scientific Reports also scores the rank 1st for the maximum numbers of citations (5472), whereas the International Journal of Numerical Methods scores the least rank with 30 citations. Considering network visualizations, one can visualize the citation network for different research sources, whereas with help of overlay visualizations, one can find that journals Scientific reports and Nanomaterials are more actively engaged in research publications, as compared to the another journals.

4. Conclusion, Limitations and Future Scope of the Research

The present section focuses on the details of conclusion, limitations and future scope of the research work:

4.1 Conclusion

Following points represent the conclusion of the research work:

- a) In last ten years, a remarkable progress in the research activities has been noticed in the field of heat exchangers and nanofluids;
- b) In last three years the research on heat exchanger and nanofluids has increased in gulf countries;
- c) Gulf countries have reported the greatest research activities for the key word heat exchanger and nanofluids;
- d) India has also shown considerable achievements considering number of publications and involvement of organizations in the research.

4.2 Limitations and Future Scope of the Research Work

Following points represent the limitations of the research work:

- a) The present research work was conducted for finite number of countries and for a tenure of 10 years only; and
- b) The research work was also made limited by considering limited number of organizations and research journals.

Following points represent the future scope of the Research

- a) An extensive research can be conducted considering a broader set of countries and for a greater tenure; and
- b) A great research may also be initiated considering a broader set of organizations as well as research journals.

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